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The effect of number of pills and dosing frequency on antiretroviral drug adherence: An assessment using two adherence monitoring measures

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Abstract

Background: Strict adherence requirement to antiretroviral drugs remains a key determinant of successful treatment outcome. Drug regimen complexity has been identified as a factor that discourages adherence to antiretroviral therapy. Several measures are available to assess drug adherence each with its strengths and weaknesses. Only few of these measures are cost effective and can be used in resource limited settings.

Objective: To determine the effect of number of pills, dosing frequency, and concomitant drugs on adherence to antiretroviral drug therapy.

Method: This is a cross-sectional study utilizing a semi-structured questionnaire. Adherence to antiretroviral therapy was measured using self-report and prescription refill. The total number of pills and the dosing frequency were calculated and its association with poor adherence tested via a logistics regression model.

Results: Majority of the respondents were females (69.5%), aged 31-40 years (42.2%), married (68.5%), had greater than one pill in their drug regimen (84%), were on twice daily regimen (56.4%) and on other non-ARV drugs (59.9%).

An assessment of the adherence levels showed that 140(37.4%) and 161(43%) of the interviewed patients had poor adherence level of $\leq 95\%$ as measured via self-report and pharmacy pick up respectively. At multivariate analysis taking other non-ARV drugs and taking 2 or more ARV pills were predictors of poor adherence to antiretroviral drugs (OR=9, 4.8-16.69) and (OR=0.19, 0.08-0.5) respectively.

Conclusion: The number of times drugs are taken in a day did not affect adherence in this study however, increased number of pills and addition of other concomitant medications to an antiretroviral regimen discouraged adherence.

Keywords: Antiretroviral therapy; Adherence measures; Self report; Prescription refill

1. Introduction

The need for near perfect adherence to highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) has remained a major pre-requisite to viral suppression and successful treatment outcome [1, 2]. The concept of adherence in the management of HIV infection is pertinent thus requires continuous monitoring and evaluation with respect to the patient and the drugs. Adherence levels below 95% have been termed sub-optimal and gives room for viral replication, drug resistance and consequently treatment failure [3, 4]. The complexity of antiretroviral drugs in terms of number of pills, food

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restrictions, cold storage requirements and dosing interval were a major Achilles heel of the earlier available antiretroviral formulations [5, 6]. They were characterized with several pills, multiple dosing times and for some of the initial protease inhibitor specifically Kaletra® soft gel capsules (Lopinavir/ritonavir), required refrigeration and this hampered to a great extent a patient's ability to cope and adhere to treatment. Antiretroviral drug formulations available for HIV treatment have evolved over the years in a bid to enhance adherence. The transition from the Lopinavir/ritonavir (133.3/33.3mg) soft gel co-formulation which required storage at 2-8°C to the 200/50 mg film coated co-formulation tablet that did not require cold storage put an end to the myriad of problems associated with the epileptic power supply which made it almost impossible to store and use this protease inhibitor in our environment [7].

The advent of fixed dose formulation was a major step taken to resolve adherence issues related to number of pills though not all drug combinations can be formulated as fixed dose formulation [8].

Co-morbidities and the development of opportunistic infections such as tuberculosis coupled with the requirement for cotrimoxazole or isoniazid prophylaxis among HIV infected individuals require additional treatment and this cannot be ignored [9, 10, and 11].

Efforts have been channeled towards reducing the complexity of antiretroviral drugs and simplifying HAART regimen however the need to address other health challenges with drug therapy which ultimately increases pill burden remains a major hurdle to addressing adherence issues [12].

Several measures have been developed to assess antiretroviral drug adherence each with its strength and weakness. Though no gold standard has been identified as a measure of adherence, methods such as self-report, pill counts, prescription refill, medication event monitoring system and biological assays have been used [13].

Self-report, pill counts, and pharmacy refill are methods that are cost effective in resource limited settings like ours. Since there is no perfect method, exploring and using at least two methods to assess adherence could help complement and confirm adherence results [3, 14].

In resource limited settings like ours it is imperative to ensure that antiretroviral therapy is adhered, to maintain patients on the first line regimen for as long as possible. The cost implication of a second and third-line regimen is much higher than that of a first line regimen [15]. As treatment complexity may interfere with patient's adherence it is necessary to investigate factors that could contribute to this as well as identify practical measures that can be used to monitor adherence. This study aims to determine the effect of number of pills dosing regimen, and concomitant drugs on adherence to antiretroviral drugs.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study design

A cross sectional study utilizing an interviewer administered semi-structured questionnaire to obtain data from the respondents. Adherence was assessed using self-report and prescription refill measures.

2.2. Study setting

This study was carried out at the HIV treatment centre domiciled in the Clinical Sciences Department of the Nigerian Institute of Medical Research located in Lagos state, Nigeria. The HIV treatment centre has been in existence for over 18 years and has enrolled over 26,000 patients since inception. The clinic offers comprehensive HIV care to adults, paediatrics as well as prevention of mother to child transmission (PMTCT) services and post exposure prophylaxis treatment. Patients' data are stored in an electronic data base designed to document and monitor patient's drug pick up pattern. The clinic has a counselling unit charged with the responsibility of counselling HIV positive individuals on antiretroviral drug adherence. The pharmacy operates a system that allows a one-on-one interaction with the patients thereby allowing an assessment of each patient's adherence to medication on clinic visits. A one, two or three-month's supply of antiretroviral drugs is prescribed to individual patients based on certain defined criteria with corresponding clinical appointments for subsequent refill. The pharmacist monitors patient's adherence to these appointments communicates and refers default cases to the counselling unit for further counselling assessment and follows up.

2.3. Study Population

The study population comprises of 374 treatment experienced HIV positive adults who gave consent, had been on treatment for over a year and were aged above 18 years. Systematic sampling was used for patient selection during the study period from June to December 2019. We excluded pregnant women, children and those who did not give consent.

2.4. Adherence Assessment

2.4.1. Self-report

Adherence using self-report entailed enquiring from the patient the number of doses they have missed in a month's regimen, in essence utilizing a 4-week recall. A non-judgemental approach was used in asking questions to allow patients give sincere responses and adherence was calculated by expressing the number of doses taken as a percentage of the total number of doses prescribed.

2.4.2. Prescription Refill

Adherence assessment via prescription refill was calculated based on the assumption that prescription filled is prescription taken. Adherence was determined based on the patient's pick-up date thus the number of days off schedule in a patient's appointment was taken into consideration. Adherence calculation was by expressing the difference between the number of days from previous refill to visit date and the number of days off schedule as a percentage of the number of days from previous refill.

2.4.3. Data Management

Data was collected using an interviewer administered semi-structured questionnaire; in addition, information on prescription refill was obtained from the clinic electronic data base. Adherence was calculated for each patient using the two measures and patients whose adherence were above or below 95% were termed good and poor respectively. Data obtained were entered into an excel spreadsheet and analyzed using SPSS Version 26. Descriptive analysis was carried out followed by multivariate analysis to determine factors associated with poor adherence.

2.4.4. Ethical Considerations

Written informed consent was obtained from the respondents and those who declined to give consent were excluded from research but given care. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the ethics committee of the institution.

3. Results

During the seven months study period, a total of 374 patients were recruited and their socio-demographic characteristic is shown in Table 1. Majority were females (69.5%), of the age group 31-40 years (42.2%), married (68.5%), attained secondary level of education (47.1%) and are Christians (94.6%). Drug related factors describing level of adherence using the two different measures and a picture of drug types and dosing frequency has been portrayed in table 2.

Using the self-report method to measure adherence, showed that 62.6% of the patients achieved $\geq 95\%$ while 57% achieved this using the prescription refill measure. Majority of the patients (84%) were taking more than 2 pills daily, on a twice daily regimen (56.4%), on other non-antiretroviral medications (59.9%) and are on the twice daily regimen of AZT/3TC/NVP (40.9%).

Table 3 shows the Multivariate analysis of some possible factors associated with poor adherence determined using outcome from self-report and prescription refill calculations. Factors such as 'taking other non-ARV drugs' ($P < 0.001$), ($O.R = 9(4.8-16.69)$) was associated with poor adherence using both measures of adherence. Taking '2 or more pills' was also found to be associated with poor adherence ($p = 0.001$) ($O.R = 0.19(0.08-0.5)$) specifically using the prescription refill measure.

Table 1 Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency N=374 (%)
Sex	
Male	114(30.5)
Female	260(69.5)
Age	
<30	68(18.2)
31-40	158(42.2)
41-50	102(27.3)
>50	46(12.3)
Marital status	
Single	78(20.9)
Married	256(68.5)
Widowed	26(6.9)
Divorced / Separated	14(3.7)
Educational Status	
Primary	80(21.3)
Secondary	176(47.1)
Tertiary	118(31.6)
Religion	
Christianity	354(94.6)
Islam	20(5.4)

Table 2 Adherence assessment and drug related factors

Drug Related Factors	Frequency N=374(%)
Self-Report	
≥95% adherence(good)	234(62.6)
<95% adherence(poor)	140(37.4)
Prescription refill	
≥95% adherence(good)	213(57.0)
<95% adherence(poor)	161(43.0)
No of Pills	
1	60(16.0)
2-7	314(84.0)
Dosing frequency	
Once	163(43.6)
Twice	211(56.4)
Other Non-ARV drugs	
Yes	224(59.9)
No	150(40.1)

Antiretroviral drug regimen	
TDF/3TC/EFV	119(31.8)
AZT/3TC/NVP	153(40.9)
ABC/3TC +NVP	44(11.8)
ABC/3TC+EFV	16(4.3)
ATV/r+ TDF/3TC	40(10.7)
LPV/r + TDF/3TC	2(0.5)

Table 3 Factors associated with poor adherence

Variable	OR	P value
Self-report Measure		
Other Non-ARV Drugs		
Yes	9(4.8-16.69)	<0.001
No	ref	
Dosing frequency		
Twice	1.36(0.81-2.29)	0.242
Once	ref	
Number of Pills		
2 or more	4.82(1.32-17.52)	0.017
1	ref	
Prescription Refill Measure		
Other Non-ARV drugs		
Yes	0.25(0.15-0.42)	<0.001
No	ref	
Dosing Times		
Twice	1.59(0.97-2.62)	0.068
Once	ref	
Number of Pills		
2 or more	0.19(0.08-0.5)	0.001
1	ref	

4. Discussion

Assessing adherence to antiretroviral drugs is a necessary step to ascertain patient's progress with therapy. The fact that no perfect measure exists has given room for exploring more than one measure to give a clearer picture. This study has used two measures that are cost effective and readily available in our environment. Poor adherence levels (<95%) were observed in 37.4% and 43% of the patients using self-report and prescription refill measures respectively. This difference is expected because no two measures can give exact result as each measure has its strengths and weakness coupled with the fact that different criteria are considered in its calculation. However, the proximity of the values could help confirm and complement adherence results. Similarly, been and his colleagues [16], in Netherlands explored self-report and prescription refill. They demonstrated that both measures could predict undetectable viral load though the self-report measure had a higher specificity compared to pharmacy refill. Other researchers have compared a

combination of two or more adherence assessment methods which we didn't use in this study and have clearly demonstrated that no two measures give exact result but complement each other [13, 17].

The complexity of treatment regimen in terms of the number of pills, dosing frequency and additional non antiretroviral drugs was investigated in this study with respect to its association with poor adherence via a logistics regression model. It was observed that at multivariate analysis 'taking additional non antiretroviral drugs' had a very strong association with poor adherence (O.R = 9(4.8-16.69) as calculated using self-report as adherence measure. It was also observed to have an association with poor adherence using the prescription refill O.R = (0.25(0.15-0.42) though a stronger association was observed with self-report. This claim is buttressed by findings of Cantundo *et al* [18] whose study reported that patients on concomitant medications to address other health conditions besides HIV infection are prone to non-adherence to antiretroviral drugs. Furthermore, some researchers demonstrated that though the simplification of ARVs has helped in improving adherence, not all patients benefit from it as its effect can be counterbalanced by the effect on non-antiretroviral drugs taken by HIV positive individuals [19, 20].

This study revealed that taking two or more antiretroviral pills per day was associated with poor adherence compared to the single fixed dose regimen (O.R =0.19(0.08-0.5) though this fact was more depicted with the prescription refill assessment. Several studies [21, 22] have all demonstrated that the single dose regimen improved adherence. Incidentally, dosing frequency was not associated with poor adherence in our study. This is contrary to findings by Buscher [23] and his colleagues who reported greater adherence with once daily dosing compared with twice daily dosing frequency. Kapadia *et al* [24] also identified in their single pill regimens yielded better virological response compared to thrice daily regimen. The reason for this difference from our study might not be clear but a further qualitative study might throw more light on this.

It is also imperative for health workers to pay more attention to other co-morbid conditions and the corresponding treatment given to HIV positive individuals as this might help give a true picture of adherence to antiretroviral drugs.

Limitation

This study used two out of the several measures of adherence. The two measures are cost effective and are what will be readily available for use in a resource limited setting.

5. Conclusion

Adherence levels obtained using the two measures differed slightly. The number of times drugs are taken in a day did not affect adherence in this study but increased number of pills and addition of other concomitant medications to an antiretroviral regimen discouraged adherence.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors declare no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the respondents and those who declined to give consent were excluded from research but given care.

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